

Electrical Impedance changes as a possible real-time indicator of Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA) efficacy

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In recent years, the use of irreversible electroporation (IRE) as a method for ablation of cardiac tissue in the treatment of cardiac arrhythmias, also known as Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA), has rapidly moved from preclinical studies to clinic. Although safety, efficacy and lesion durability of the treatments have been recently demonstrated in limited groups of patients, studies in larger groups of individuals are still under development to show comparative evidence of its superiority against radiofrequency ablation and cryoablation.

One of the many open questions of this new technology is how the local electrical activity of electroporated myocardial tissue is modified during treatment and the differences between the reversibly and irreversibly damaged areas. This leads to question if the measurement of local electrograms, which are usually registered during ablation with thermal methods, can accurately reflect the treatment outcome and motivates the research on new real-time lesion assessment methods.

In this in vivo study we performed a parametric study using bursts of high frequency biphasic square waveforms of different amplitudes and frequencies leading to different levels of ablation efficacy. They consisted on square biphasic bursts (10 bursts of 100 μ s separated 1 s) at three different frequencies (90, 260 and 450 kHz) and two fixed voltages (500 and 800 V_p), additional a group of monophasic 100 μ s square pulses at 500 V was also studied. PFA in vivo treatments were performed in Sprague-Dawley rats following a protocol approved by the Sant Pau Hospital Animal Experimentation Ethical Committee. Under general anesthesia, a left thoracotomy was made to create a surgical window. A monopolar epicardial electrode was carefully positioned over the left

ventricle epicardium and a return electrode patch was attached to the back of the animals. During the procedure we continuously recorded the temperature at the electrode tip, the ECG and muscle contractions. In-burst electrical impedance was calculated from the acquired voltage and electric current waveforms. Once the catheter was in position, baseline electrical impedance was recorded using 4 low voltage (50 V_p) bursts identical to the treatment waveforms, subsequently, high voltage treatment bursts were applied. Twenty-one days later, animals were euthanized and the hearts were fixed for histological analysis with Masson's trichrome staining to assess the extent of fibrotic lesions. Our results show a clear dependence of ablation lesion size with frequency and amplitude of the applied waveform. This demonstrates how the IRE lethal threshold value increases with the increase in the frequency of the applied waveform. The analysis of the impedance changes suggests that the impedance magnitude drop measured during PFA applications correlates with the chronic ablation lesions observed. These preliminary results suggest the possible use of electrical impedance as a real-time indicator of PFA efficacy.